

Paper 5

INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

Education is the light of individual. In fact, the success and worth of every one’s life is based on his/her level of education. The process and quality the nation is passed by the level of education. Our constitution guarantees the education for all people of our nation. The flagship programme of our nation “Sarve Shikshana Abhiyana” moto is ‘Education for all, Not for Selected, Each One Teach One.’ A brief definition of Inclusive education is provided by Lip-Sky & Gartner (1996, 1999), who described it as students with disabilities having full membership in age-appropriate classes in their neighbourhood schools with appropriate supplementary aids and support services. Inclusive Education on all learners, with or without disabilities being able to learn together access to common school setting with support services. To offer a general education in ordinary, special day or special residential school setting accordance to their needs. To prepare them for integration into ordinary schools or society, and meet their psychological needs for security, love and affection, acceptance and success. To teach them the basic daily living skills for independent living. To enhanced their social development including their inter-personal relationship. To break the barrier of poverty by the development and empowerment of society through education. Inclusive education is focus on all learners, with or without disabilities being able to learn together access to common school setting with support services. It is also concerned with fostering mutually sustaining relationships between schools and communities.

Keywords: “Sarve Shikshana Abhiyana” moto is ‘Education for all, Not for Selected, Each One Teach One.’

INTRODUCTION

Education is the light of individual. In fact, the success and worth of every one’s life is based on his/her level of education. The process and quality the nation is assed by the level of education. Our constitution guarantees the education for all people of our nation. The flagship programme of

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our nation “Sarve Shikshana Abhiyana” moto is ‘Education for all, Not for Selected, Each One Teach One.’

It is a crime to be illiterate in a democratic society. Education is a pre requisite for democracy. Democracy cannot function in an illiterate society. So democracy requires everybody to be educated. It is not only democratic concern but also need for the economic, social and cultural development of country.

Inclusive Education is not only about addressing issues of inputs, such as access and those related to processes such as teacher training, but that it involves a shift in underlying values and beliefs held across the system.

CONCEPT

A brief definition of Inclusive education is provided by Lip-Sky & Gartner (1996, 1999), who described it as students with disabilities having full membership in age-appropriate classes in their neighbourhood schools with appropriate supplementary aids and support services. It includes all the students who are away from the education for any reason like physically or mentally challenged, economically, socially, deprived or belonging to any caste, creed, gender etc.

➤ **MEANING** Inclusive education means that all students attend and are welcomed by their neighbourhood school in age appropriate, regular classes and are supported to learn, contribute and participate in all aspect of the life of the school. It is about how we develop and design our schools, class rooms, programmes and activities so that all students learn and participate together.

Inclusive Education is educating all students in age-appropriate general education class in their neighbourhood school, with high quality instructions, interventions and supports so all students can be successful in the core curriculum. Inclusive schools have a collaborative and respectful school culture where students with disabilities are presumed to be competent, develop positive social relationship with peers, and fully participating members of the school community.

Inclusion in education is an approach to educating students with special educational need. Under the inclusion model, students with special needs spent most or all of their time with non-disabled students. Inclusion rejects the use of special school or class rooms to separate students with disabilities from students without disabilities

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➤ **DEFINITION** UNESCO defines Inclusive Education as “A process of addressing and responding to the diversity of needs of all learners through increasing participation in learning, cultures and communities, and reducing exclusion within and from education. It involves changes and modifications in content, approaches, structures and strategies, with a common vision with all children of the appropriate age range and a conviction that it is the responsibility of the state to educate all children.” It is not marginal issue, but is central to the achievement of high-quality education for all learners and development of more inclusive societies. It can be defined as the process of increasing the participation of students in the cultures, curricula and communities of local mainstream schools.

SCOPE

Inclusive Education on all learners, with or without disabilities being able to learn together access to common school setting with support services. It allows all type of students to participate and learn common knowledge and skills in inclusive school set up. The goal is to provide a personalized education for all students within the context of general class room. Following type of children are included for inclusive education.

- Children of remote area
- Working children
- Girls- from different situation
- Migrant children
- Disabled children
- Orphan children
- Street children
- HIV children

OBJECTIVE

- To ensure the quality of education to all students.
- To respond to the diverse needs of all students.
- To gain social equality, eliminate prejudices and discrimination.
- To achieve the goal of education for all but not for few.

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- To develop sense of self confidence and social prestige.
- To accept diversity as normal and as a rich source for all students.
- Utilisation of science and technology.
- To improve the quality of education.
- To recognize, accept diversity and fulfilment of constitutional responsibility.
- To value the every life equally and put inclusive value in action.
- To help everyone feel a sense of belonging and promote children’s participation in learning and teaching.
- To reduce exclusion, discrimination and barriers to learning and participation.

AIMS

- To offer a general education in ordinary, special day or special residential school setting accordance to their needs.
- To prepare them for integration into ordinary schools or society, and meet their psychological needs for security, love and affection, acceptance and success.
- To teach them the basic daily living skills for independent living.
- To enhanced their social development including their inter-personal relationship.
- To break the barrier of poverty by the development and empowerment of society through education.
- To help them realize their limitations, potential and develop a realistic & positive outlook towards life.
- To cultivate interests and hobbies for improving their quality of life.
- To provide them with medical and other auxiliary services such as physiotherapy, Occupational therapy, speech therapy, career and vocational counselling.
- To compensate for their loss of life experience due to mobility difficulties through organized excursion and outdoor activities.
- To develop cultures, policies and practices to promote diversity and respect for everyone.
- To improve the school for staff and parents as well as children.
- To emphasize the value of building positive school communities as well achievements.

IMPORTANCE

When children with and without disabilities are included, they learn more- Percentage of courses students with learning disabilities take in general education classrooms is related to both their academic performance and their social adjustment at school. Students along with disability students are learnt and achieve more. When they are included, students with disabilities have:

- Greater access to the general education curriculum.
- More time “on task”.
- More academic gains.
- More progress on literacy skills.
- Increased communication skills.

Inclusion leads to lower rate of suspension and drop out and to higher rates of employment-

Students with a range of disabilities, it is found that more time spent in a general education classroom, positively correlated with fewer absence from school, disruptive behaviour and better outcomes after school in the areas of employment and independent living.

ADVANTAGE

- Develop individual strengths and gifts, with high and appropriate expectations for each child.
- Work on individual goals while participating in the life of the classroom with other students their own age.
- Involve their parents in their education and in the activities of their local schools.
- Develop friendships with a wide variety of other children, each with their own individual needs and abilities.
- Positively affect both their school and community to appreciate diversity and inclusion on a broader level.
- All children are able to be part of their community and develop a sense of belonging and become better prepared for life in the community as children and adults.
- It provides better opportunities for learning. Children with varying abilities are often better motivated when they learn classes surrounded by other children.

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- The expectations of all the children are higher. Successful inclusion attempts to develop an individual’s strengths and gifts.
- Disabled or challenged students may get a support and help from normal students.
- All the students excluded from school because of some reason may get a chance to enjoy school life with normal students.
- It can produce positive changes in attitudes within schools towards diversity by educating all children together and leading to greater social cohesion.
- It help the disabled child to developed a sense of pride in their work because they actually fill like they accomplished something.

FACTORS AFFECTING INCLUSION The following factors are affecting the inclusion in the classroom.

- **Expense** Funding is a major constraint to the practice of inclusion. Teaching students with disabilities in general education classrooms takes specialists and additional staff to support student’s need. Inadequate funding can hinder ongoing professional development that keeps both specialists and classroom teachers updated on the best practice of inclusion.
- **MIS-INFORMATION** Some of the greatest factors associated with inclusion in education are negative attitudes. As with society in general, these attitudes and stereotypes are often caused by a lack of knowledge and understanding. The attitudes and abilities of general education teachers and para educators in particular can be major limitation in inclusive education.
- **ACCESSIBILITY** Obviously, a students with a disability cannot learn in an inclusive classroom if he/she cannot enter the room, let alone the school building. Some schools are still inaccessible to students in wheelchairs or to those others mobility aids and need elevators, ramps, paved pathways and lifts to get in around buildings. Schools and classrooms must be able to accessible and accommodate a student’s assistive technology devices as well as other furniture to meet individual needs.
- **EDUCATIONAL MODIFICATION** Just as the environment must be accessible to students with disabilities, the curriculum must facilitate inclusive education. General educator must be willing to work with inclusion specialists to make modifications and accommodations in both teaching methods, classroom and homework assignments

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- **CO-OPERATION** One of the final factors associated with inclusion education is a lack of communication among administrators, teachers, specialist, staff, parents and students. Open communication and coordinated planning between general education teachers and special education staff are essential for inclusion to work. Collaboration must also exist among teachers, staff, and parents to meet a student’s needs and facilitate learning at home.

CONCLUSION

Inclusive Education is focus on all learners, with or without disabilities being able to learn together access to common school setting with support services. It is also concerned with fostering mutually sustaining relationships between schools and communities. It is not only about addressing issues of input, such as access, and those related to process such as teacher training, but that it involves a shift in under laying values and beliefs held across the system. It is also help to all children, including children with disabilities, not only have access to schooling within their own community, but that they are provided with appropriate learning opportunities to achieve their full potential. All children should have equivalent and systematic learning opportunities in a wide range of school and additional education setting, despite the difference that might exist. It is also provides following understanding in education:-

- The open learning potential of each student.
- Reform of the curriculum and a cross cutting pedagogy.
- Active participation of students in the learning process.
- A common curriculum for all, based upon differentiated and/or individualized instruction.
- Involves the process of increasing the participating of students in and reducing their exclusion from, the cultures curricula and communities of local schools.
- Concern with improving schools for staff as well as for students.
- Involves restructuring the cultures, policies and practices in school so that they respond to the diversity of students in their locality.
- A concern with overcoming barriers to the access and participation of particular students may reveal gaps in the attempts of a school to respond to diversity more generally.
- Inclusion in education is one aspect of inclusion in society.
